

ISSUES OF CRIMINAL LIABILITY FOR HIV/AIDS INFECTION IN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN LEGISLATION

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Abstract: In this article, the author examines one of the most pressing problems facing the entire international community and each individual country. Proposals are made to improve the current legislation through a comparative analysis of the criminal legislation of various foreign countries and the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Key words: *Criminal liability, disease transmission, completion, infectious diseases, foreign experience.*

Throughout its history, humanity has faced various infectious diseases. The underdevelopment of medicine, the difficulties of maintaining personal hygiene in people's daily lives, the organization of work related to the treatment of the sick by separating them from the healthy is a natural tendency that has passed away along with human civilizations. Although humanity has achieved great heights in science and

discovered medicines that are effective against diseases previously considered incurable, this is a natural process that has been repeated throughout history. For example, in our lives we still encounter complications of the COVID-19 problem, which in recent years has become an epidemic, has claimed the lives of many people, especially the elderly and young children, and even paralyzed the medicine of developed countries. Another such disease is genital-cutaneous diseases and HIV/AIDS infections, which are predominantly transmitted sexually and through blood. First of all, it should be said that this disease could be transmitted to humans from monkeys living in Africa many years ago. Later, among the immoral sections of society, mainly among prostitutes and homosexuals. In 1978, it was identified among the USA, Sweden and some African countries¹. In 1980, in Atlanta (USA), 5 men were hospitalized with pneumonia. It was later discovered that they were homosexuals who used needles and that their illness was the early stages of HIV². Around this time, the disease began to spread throughout the world. For example, in 1987, a translator who lived for a long time in Africa in the territory of the former USSR was diagnosed with HIV. After this, in 1988, a woman from Leningrad died of AIDS³. Thus, in many countries of the world, with the increasing number of deaths from this disease, innovations and additions to legislation began.

Article 113 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for liability not only for the transmission of HIV/AIDS, but also for creating a danger of its transmission⁴. This responsibility has existed since September 22, 1994, when our Criminal Code was first adopted with some minor changes and additions.

¹ Margolis L.B. HIV infection: from biology to politics / L.B. Margolis // Labor and social relations. 2018. No. 11. - P.71-79.

² <https://gcaids.kz/ru/stati/26-istoriya-poyavleniya-vich>

³ <https://xn--d1achwgkbn7a.xn--p1ai/yse-o-vich-i-spid/istoriya-virusa/>

⁴ Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan [with amendments and additions until July 1, 2020] - T.: <<Publishing legal literature>>, 2020. -512 p (75 p)

Before talking about the subject of the article, it should be said that “the object of a crime is a system of social relations between people who have been harmed as a result of a crime, protected by criminal law”⁵.

Article 113 of the Criminal Code is located in Chapter III of the Code, that is, in terms of crimes dangerous to life or health. According to M.Kh. Rustambaev, “the direct object of the crime is social relations that ensure the safety of human life or health”⁶. Some scientists say that only health is the priority object, others consider human life to be the main object⁷. Agreeing with the opinion of the two above-mentioned authors, we can say that if we analyze the crime horizontally, then the main object is, first of all, human life. An additional object is human health. Epidemiologically, it is natural that the health of other people is also at risk.

From an objective point of view, part 1 of Article 113 of the Criminal Code is reflected in the deliberate creation of a risk of transmission of a sexually transmitted disease. One of the necessary signs here is that the person must know that he or she has a sexually transmitted disease. If a person is sick with a sexually transmitted disease, the medical personnel who registered the person and conducted a medical consultation will definitely warn that the person will be prosecuted if he/she infects or exposes the person to the risk of infection. The risk of infection must be real. That is, a person made enough efforts to become infected, but due to accident or the efforts of the victim to protect himself/herself from the disease, he/she does not become infected with the disease. The

⁵ Criminal law. General part: textbook / ed. A.N. Tarbagaeva. – Moscow: Prospekt, 2011. P.97

⁶ Rustambaev M.Kh. Course of criminal law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Volume 3. Special part. Crimes against the person Crimes against peace and security. Textbook. 2nd edition, supplemented and revised - T.: Military-Technical Institute of the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2018. 152 p

⁷ Norvartyan. Yu.S. On the issue of the direct object of infection with venereal disease and HIV infection // Bulletin of the Samara Humanitarian Academy. Series: Law. 2013 №1. // URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-voprosu-o-neposredstvennom-obekte-zarazheniya-venericheskoy-boleznyu-i-vich-infektsiev>

second part of the article provides for liability for the transmission of sexually transmitted diseases. Here, the disease is mainly caused by the fact that the accused had unprotected sex and lived in an irregular sexual relationship. The disease can also be transmitted through careless use of hygiene products. Regardless of how the infection occurred, it does not affect qualifications. The objective aspects of the following parts of the article are presented in a similar way. Only part 5 of Article 113 highlights the objective side. That is, the disease is contracted due to the fact that the subject has not performed or fulfilled his professional duties, which he performs every day.

In general, not only for this, but also for other crimes, the objective side of the crime is an action or system of actions that manifests the external side of the crime, leading to harm to the object. According to V.N. Kudryavtsev, "... the objective side of a crime is a socially dangerous and unlawful encroachment on interests protected by law, viewed from the outside, from the point of view of the sequential development of events and developments, starting with the criminal act or inaction of the subject and ending with the process of creating a criminal result⁸.

From the subjective side, parts 1-4 of Article 113 were committed intentionally. Intention can be of both types. A person who knowingly suffers from a sexually transmitted disease or HIV/AIDS infection infects the victim or exposes him/her to the risk of infection. In episode 5 alone, a person becomes infected with a disease due to negligence. The motive is mainly material gain through self-interest and it does not affect qualifications.

The subject of the crime is a sane person who has reached the age of 16 and is aware of the presence of genital disease or HIV/AIDS. Only in part 5 of the article, the

⁸ Kudryavtsev V.N. The objective side of the crime. M.: Gosyurizdat, 1960. P.9.

topic of the introduction is considered special, and we are talking mainly about medical workers and cosmetology. As Chuchaev reported⁹.

If we turn to the legislation of foreign countries, then, first of all, it should be said that the criminal legislation of some countries provides for a special norm for the transmission of HIV/AIDS or other venereal diseases. In particular, special standards have been established in some states of the Russian Federation, Ukraine, Belarus, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Moldova, Georgia, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Estonia, and Australia.

In the legislation of some countries, this is qualified as a general crime against human health, taking into account harm to human life or health. I will give examples. For example, in the Swiss Criminal Code there is no special provision regarding AIDS, but we see in the code articles that define general responsibility for the transmission of dangerous infectious diseases¹⁰.

If you look at the legislation of the country of Singapore, Article 269 of the Criminal Code provides for liability for the careless transmission of an infectious disease, and Article 270 provides for liability for the intentional transmission of an infectious disease¹¹. The list of infectious diseases is determined by a special law.

If we analyze the Criminal Law of the Chinese state, we can see that the Criminal Code there also provides for liability for the transmission of infectious diseases. Here, as in Singapore, the Law “On the Prevention and Treatment of Infectious

⁹ Commentary on the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation (article-by-article) / Ed. Doctor of Law sciences, prof. A.I. Chuchaeva. - M.: "CONTRACT", 2012. - 624 p.

¹⁰ Swiss criminal code. // URL: <http://okpravo.ru/zarubezhnoe-pravo/ugolovnoe-pravo-zarubezhnyh-stran%B8.html?ysclid=laxxm4etxb316113286>

¹¹ Burdinskaya A.N. Criminal infection with the human immunodeficiency virus: criminal legal and criminological assessment: dis. Ph.D. criminal science: 12.00.08. - Vladivostok, 2017.

Diseases” of 02/21/1989 is in force¹². This law defines which diseases are dangerous infectious diseases.

Now we will talk about the end time of the crime, which is an objective sign of the crime of spreading HIV/AIDS, analyze the current legislation, and then make a general conclusion about the article.

It is known that determining the moment of completion of a crime is a guarantee of the correct qualification of the act, respectively, bringing or not bringing a person to criminal responsibility and assigning him/her a fair punishment¹³. But a detailed classification of the end time of crimes has not yet been fully studied in science¹⁴. In criminal law, in order to recognize a crime as completed, the act of a person who intentionally committed a socially dangerous act has all the signs of a crime - it is considered completed¹⁵.

Before talking about the moment of completion of the crime of spreading HIV infection/AIDS, it should be said that the HIV virus is the causative agent of a chronic infectious immunodeficiency disease. HIV infection is a chronic infectious immunodeficiency disease caused by the human immunodeficiency virus. AIDS is the final stage of HIV infection, when symptoms of the disease appear as a result of damage to the human immune system¹⁶. So far, several million people around the world have died from this infectious, chronic, long-term disease¹⁷. Since the disease became an

¹² Burdinskaya A.N. Criminal infection with the human immunodeficiency virus: criminal legal and criminological assessment: dis. Ph.D. criminal science: 12.00.08. - Vladivostok, 2017. P 50

¹³ Baymakova N.N. Completed crime and the moment of completion of the crime // Russian justice. 2010. - No. 9 p 45

¹⁴ Kudryavtsev V.N. General theory of classification of crimes. - M., 1999 p 77

¹⁵ See: Babiy N.A. Criminal law of the Republic of Belarus. General part: Lecture notes. Mn., 2000. P. 109; Commentary on the Criminal Code of the RSFSR / Ed. Yu.D. Severina. M., 1985 p 32-34

¹⁶ ON COUNTERING THE SPREAD OF THE DISEASE CAUSED BY THE HUMAN IMMUNODEFICIENCY VIRUS (HIV INFECTION) LRU-353 web: <https://lex.uz/docs/-2240470>

¹⁷ World Health Organization statistics.web: <https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/themes/hiv-aids>

international epidemic in the late 1980s, countries have criminalized the spread of HIV/AIDS. Part 4 of Article 113 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan directly establishes criminal liability for creating a threat of infection or exposure to HIV/AIDS.

To legally analyze the timing of the completion of the above article, we need to pay attention to the keywords in the disposition of the article. Here the terms “knowingly” and “putting at risk of infection” acquire special significance for qualification. In particular, the fact that a person knows that he/she is sick with HIV, in order to commit this crime, legally after initial and subsequent consultations with the medical staff of AIDS centers, the person is registered in the electronic registry. If there is a risk of contracting this infection, it is expressed in a written warning about the existence of criminal liability. If a person did not officially know that he/she had an infection, was not warned of criminal liability for spreading it or exposing others to the risk of infection, and was not provided with the necessary information about it, then the person will not be the subject of criminal prosecution of this crime. For a person to be charged with infecting a victim with HIV, the risk must be real and obvious. The risk here cannot be based on imaginary, hypothetical assumptions of the victim or the accused. Also, during the qualification process, investigative and judicial authorities must carefully consider the fact that the danger should be a real, in which case they must effectively use the latest medical advances. For example, many years ago, science confirmed that eating from the same bowl, kissing and getting saliva into the mouth, as well as through airborne droplets, people do not transmit HIV.

It is important to focus on "transmission" when the victim is exposed to or at risk of becoming infected with HIV. This act, which represents the objective side, is the

act that forms the basis of the article. Legally, transmission is defined as the actual transmission of a disease to another person, regardless of the consequences¹⁸.

Infection occurs through medication in the form of pathogenesis. Pathogenesis consists of different stages, and at the first stage there is a latent period of the disease. In this case, the infection begins to multiply secretly. This process mainly depends on the sensitivity of the body's immune system and its resistance to diseases. With HIV infection, this stage can occur in different periods. For example, from 3 weeks to 2-3 months or longer. At the next stage, a person develops general symptoms of the disease, but it is difficult to diagnose what kind of disease and what symptoms a person has. At the next stage, the human immune system begins to produce antibodies against the virus in large quantities, and it becomes possible to diagnose the person.

As we mentioned above, the time when the crime ends is important, for example, the moment of its ending. When subsequently classifying a crime, the conditions and legislation existing at that time are taken into account. In criminal law, crimes by their legal nature are divided into crimes of material and formal content. Some scientists also consider types of crimes with a cut-off structure to be a separate independent direction¹⁹. The timing of the crime is of particular importance in the case of crimes of a fragmented nature. In the case of crimes with disparate content, the legislator postpones the end of the crime to the previous stage. According to M.Kh. Rustambaev, this is due to the extremely high social danger of certain crimes²⁰. In the

¹⁸ The commentary to the criminal code of the Russian Federation with article-by-article materials and judicial practice / edited. S.I. Nikulin. - M.: «Norma», 2002. - P. 351

¹⁹ See in particular: Commentary on the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation / Rep. ed. V.M. Lebedev. - 10th ed., revised. and additional - M.: "Urayt", 2010. - P. 93; Commentary on the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation / Ed. A.V. Brilliantova. - M.: "Urayt", 2009, p 8

²⁰ Rustambaev M.Kh. Course of criminal law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Volume 1. The doctrine of crime. Textbook. 2nd edition, supplemented and revised - T.: Military-Technical Institute of the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2018. p 265

case of material crimes, the time of completion of the crime is considered to be the moment the consequences occur. For crimes with a formal content, the consequence is not a condition for recognizing the crime as completed. For example, in the case of insult or slander, the crime is considered completed if the person humiliates the honor and dignity of the victim with verbal or physical gestures and hand movements. The level of harm to the defendant's health does not affect qualifications.

We divide the crime provided for in Article 113 Part 4 of the Criminal Code into two parts. 1. Knowingly expose someone to the risk of contracting HIV/AIDS. 2. Transmission infection with HIV/AIDS.

In the first case, the end of the crime actually occurs when the person, from a medical point of view, is in real danger of contracting an infection. Here, the infection should not have been transmitted accidentally or through the actions of the victim. The problem is that, as we said above, to diagnose whether a person has HIV, medical workers rely on the presence of antibodies against the virus in the blood through an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay²¹. Their manifestation takes a long time, say, several months, even years. There are few investigative and judicial procedural deadlines that must be adhered to and wait for the latent period of virus growth. For example, a woman, her name is A, working in a salon, gave her blood to test, to the AIDS center and received a “positive” answer. She was warned under Article 113 of the Criminal Code. They explained to her that she couldn’t engage in this profession in the future; if she continued, it would endanger people’s lives. But as it continues to operate as a primary source of income, it exposes many people to the risk of contracting HIV.

²¹ Norvartyan, Yu. S. About the moment of the end of infection with venereal disease and HIV infection / Yu. S. Norvartyan // Society and law. – 2012. – No. 5(42). p 136-139.
Also see: What is an ELISA? link: <https://www.thermofisher.com/uz/en/home/life-science/protein-biology/protein-biology-learning-center/protein-biology-resource-library/pierce-protein-methods/overview-elisa.html>

The main difficulties encountered in prosecuting a person named A. are as follows: 1. As a result of the person receiving antiretroviral therapy and taking medications regularly, there is a 0% chance of spreading the disease to others. Thus, she did not endanger others, and the fact that she received an income and continued her work was a socially useful act. 2. The person has already transmitted HIV to others, but her clients have tested negative for HIV. The reason is that, as a result of the latent period of virus reproduction, all processes in them are hidden, so it is now impossible to detect the virus in them. It is clear from this that it is difficult to determine the end time of the crime here.

In the second case, a person knowingly infected another person with HIV. Let's say citizen A. several months ago had unprotected sex with B., who was engaged in providing intimate services to clients. After some time, HIV infection was detected in A., who also had unprotected sex with persons named C. and D. Based on the results of the investigation, citizens B., S., D. are already sick with HIV and were warned under Article 113. But because of the medications they take, they are less likely to pass the disease on to another person. In this case, the question should be considered of who and when infected the victim with HIV infection and when the end of the crime occurred, or whether all B., V., D. should be responsible for putting them at risk. The risk of contracting HIV by implicating them all as defendants in the case is problematic. One side of the problem is the slowness of the development of medicine, and the other returns to the issues of specifying legislation, including, as an addition, a rule providing for exemption from liability. Taking into account the current trend, the Supreme Court - under Article 113 as a decision should provide clarification on the current issue facing the legislation.

To summarize the above, first of all, it should be said that AIDS, being one of the infectious and dangerous diseases that can be fatal, is an issue that is always in the spotlight at the global level. States have criminalized AIDS in their criminal laws so that they can fight it legally. In particular, Uzbekistan demonstrated its legal position regarding this disease with Article 113 of the Criminal Code. In the legislation of foreign countries, if in some Asian countries, for example in Uzbekistan, the fight against the spread of AIDS is carried out through a special norm, then in some countries general responsibility for all dangerous infectious diseases has been established. Based on the presented analytical data, we considered it necessary to make the following proposals.

1. Part 4 of Article 113 of our Criminal Code, that is, “knowingly creating a danger of infecting another person with HIV/AIDS or infecting him/her with HIV/AIDS” should be with separate sanctions. To be clear, there should be a separate, lighter sanction for exposing someone to HIV/AIDS, and a more severe sanction for direct transmission.

2. In practice, we see that, given the mentality of our people, cases of persons accused of exposing themselves to the risk of contracting HIV/AIDS, for example, basically, citizens who started a family after entering into a Sharia marriage must be settled by reconciliation in the absence of a claim by the victim, that is, by amending Article 66¹ of the Criminal Code of the Uzbekistan, regardless of what part of Article 113 the person committed a socially dangerous act, it is possible to reconcile offender and victim (at the moment parts 3-4-5 of article 113 are not agreed upon).

3. Study in more depth infectious diseases that are as dangerous as HIV/AIDS in the life of society, and introduce into legislation the issue of criminal liability for intentional infection by them. In this case, regulate all infectious diseases in one article, using a single law or taking into account the fact that such crimes to one degree or

another harm human health, and hold persons accountable for contracting an infectious disease under Article 105 of the Criminal Code or Article 104, depending on the consequences, and thereby destigmatize people who have HIV/AIDS and de-identify them.

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